

Research and Innovation Action

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

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Report on **Milestone 39**

Launch Expertise Strategy

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Abstract:

This document describes the launch of *D6.2 SSHOC Building Expertise Strategy* and the related activities and tasks, proposed after the first year of the SSHOC project. It focuses on planning the initial iteration of the SSHOC Training Toolkit release and efforts to organize Train-the-trainer bootcamps and the SSHOC Stakeholder Forum.

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1. Introduction

This milestone concerns the launching of the expertise strategy. Means of verification as defined in the SSHOC DoA are the activities related to the start of planning of (a) initial iteration of the toolkit release, (b) bootcamps and (c) the Stakeholder Forum.

Planning relates to the work done in WP6, T6.2 and T6.4 to set good grounds for mentioned events and toolkit with which the project wants to engage SSH trainers and other stakeholders in developing even better products in the framework of the SSHOC project and raise awareness on the work done so far.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1. Role of the Milestone

SSHOC WP6 is engaging and training stakeholders on the products and outputs of the SSHOC project through different activities. Engagement strategy on awareness workshops and webinars was already described in the report of MS38. What is described in this report are the steps made to:

- Deliver the mid-project SSHOC Stakeholder Forum to showcase project progress and achievements and engage with a broader range of SSHOC stakeholders and other European initiatives.
- Develop a SSHOC Training Toolkit.
- Organize and deliver three geographically distributed SSHOC Train-the-trainer bootcamps to national training organizations.

2.2. Means of verification

Among events that SSHOC is planning for its stakeholders are a mid-project Stakeholder forum and train-the-trainer bootcamps. The forum is being organized by partners of WP6 T6.2 and WP2, with contribution of all

WPs. Development of Training Toolkit and planning of Train-the-Trainers Bootcamps was done by WP6 T6.4 partners. Steps taken to organize events are described in this section. It is the case that events originally planned in mid-2020 will not be taking place due to travel and gathering restrictions made by national governments following the COVID19-crisis.

2.2.1. Training Toolkit release (T6.4)

The SSHOC Training Toolkit will be a collection of training materials that SSH trainers can reuse in their own training activities. A first version of the toolkit will be released at the beginning of April. The toolkit will be described in more detail in MS40 SSHOC Training Toolkit (preliminary version) and D6.9 SSHOC Training Toolkit (draft) which are both due to be submitted to the EC at the end of April 2020.

The Toolkit development has been based on the work done in WP6 T6.3 that collected information on existing learning materials in a drupal-based application. The application, which is described in more detail in D6.7 Inventory of Existing Learning Materials, is used and further developed with T6.3 partners' contribution to become the Training Toolkit, collecting materials specifically directed at trainers and data-stewards. In February 2020, an internal document to collect materials for trainers and data stewards has been set-up and the team started populating this document with training materials and suggestions for additional metadata for types of (train-the-trainer) resources such as types of learning resources, common topics. In March 2020, the curation of collected training materials began and additional arrangements have been made for the usability, branding and promotion of the Training Toolkit before its official launch. The SSHOC Training Toolkit will be an online inventory collecting information on training materials from various sources, including SSHOC partners (e.g. CESSDA, DARIAH) and will identify nodes, which provide local training for SSH scholars. The toolkit will contain materials from a range of topics including Research Data Management, FAIR Data, Open Science as well as materials on training development and didactics. Trainers can find various types of materials, including, for instance, modules, workshops, slides, videos and games. After the initial release of the SSHOC Training Toolkit in April, the toolkit will be further developed and expanded based on feedback from the SSHOC Training Community and the participants of the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps, described in the next section. The SSHOC Training Community was launched in September 2019¹ and its activities are described in the upcoming deliverable D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training network.

2.2.2 Train-the-trainer bootcamps (T6.4)

SSHOC will organize three train-the-trainer bootcamps targeting SSH trainers from the SSHOC Training Community and beyond. These train-the-trainer bootcamps will be used to present and collect feedback on the SSHOC Training Toolkit, as well as to help trainers develop and improve their own training activities.

Two of the three bootcamps were planned in 2020 and accepted to take place along two major conferences. Due to the COVID19-crisis, these events will not take place as planned. The first bootcamp was planned at the

¹ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/launch-sshoc-training-community-0>

IASSIST conference in Sweden in May 2020, targeting social science scholars and the data archive community (see Appendix 3). The second bootcamp was planned at the LIBER conference in Serbia in June 2020, targeting librarians and including a hands-on session, using CLARIN training materials (see Appendix 4). IASSIST 2020 has been fully postponed to 2021, whereas LIBER will hold parts of the conference, including workshops, online. WP6 and, more specifically T6.4, is currently working on a mitigation plan, in order to address the new situation and still build and empower the SSHOC Training Community. For this purpose, T6.4 will attempt to take elements of the bootcamps online, also taking into account feedback from the Training Community kick-off and the SSHOC 3rd Consortium Meeting (both taking place in the second part of March). Potential formats of future face-to-face bootcamps and/or events complementary to the online sessions will be foreseen in the mitigation plan, taking into account our Grant Agreement commitments, the best interest of both the project and our community, as well as the COVID-19 crisis developments.

As WP6 will organize the last bootcamp in 2021, it was proposed to postpone the final deliverable describing the bootcamps (D6.12) as well as the deliverable of the final version of the toolkit (D6.11) and its related milestone (MS41) to include the bootcamp results in the toolkit.

2.2.3 Stakeholder Forum (T6.2)

The planning of the event started with an overview of conferences/events happening in mid-2020 that unite various stakeholders. Close communication with members of WP2, WP6 and the project coordinator led to identify ESOF2020 conference² (July in Trieste, Italy), that is aiming at approximately 4000 attendees from different disciplines and stakeholder communities, to best fit the needs. Call for proposals was at the time already closed, and communication with organizers on the structure of the event led the organizing committee to the decision to collocate the event and hold it on the last day of the main conference, that is on July 9th. The use of ESOF promotion channels to attract stakeholders to the SSHOC event was planned.

Further work went in two directions. First to try to find an appropriate place, and second to involve other EOSC Clusters (namely ENVRI-FAIR, PaNOSC, ESCAPE and EOSC-Life) in co-organizing the event. Ideally, the forum would include all clusters, reach 150-200 attendees (from different stakeholders) and be recorded (and live streamed). Work started in late November with communication via e-mails and online meetings every two weeks, which is still ongoing. Organizers of ESOF informed us that there are no large enough rooms available on the premises of the main conference. After visiting various venues on February 10th 2020 (National Hall with the Department of Legal, Language, Interpreting and Translation Studies of UNI Trieste; the International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Miramar-Trieste and main University campus) "H3 building" at the campus was selected as a venue (has large rooms, air-condition, space for catering, and coffee/poster breaks). In order to set the budget and check availability of different rooms and services, WP6 have contacted the university service office, catering team and three video-recording teams. Rooms were reserved, daily rate for rooms received, communication with recording companies (one from Ljubljana and two from Trieste) on different possibilities

² <https://www.esof.eu/en/>

have started, but catering options were left on hold due to the close-down of the UNI Trieste in relation to COVID19-crisis.

A 'purpose and scope' document was produced for the event and a preliminary programme was drafted (see Appendix 1 and Appendix 2). Some of the possible speakers were contacted and the discussions to align with SSHOC WP leaders on the content and structure of the event has started. Additional to the work done in SSHOC, a proposal to co-organize Stakeholder Forum with other EOSC clusters came to the table. EOSC coordinators expressed interest in a joint event at the past EOSC Symposium and the "EOSC services, connections and the RDA" side-event at the 14th RDA Plenary. After lengthy discussions with EOSC clusters communication and training teams it became obvious that other clusters are not ready for this kind of engagements yet. A decision was made, at the beginning of March 2020, to go ahead with organizing this as a solely SSHOC Stakeholder Forum, with clusters possibly collaborating on sessions presenting some of their tools and services that are of interest to the SSHOC stakeholder communities. Parallel to the stakeholder forum, a hackathon was also planned to focus on the Marketplace. A call was prepared targeting participants from all EOSC cluster projects and new projects like TRIPLE to participate in the hackathon.

Due to the current health situation caused by COVID-19 pandemic, the Stakeholder Forum needs to be postponed and the team is exploring other events to possibly collocate with, such as the EOSC Symposium in October or ESOF itself that was postponed to September.

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

The reason for the agreed postponement of the delivery of this milestone was the agreed postponement of work on MS40 Training Toolkit (preliminary version) and D6.9 SSHOC Training Toolkit. The Milestone was postponed from January 2020 to March 2020, with no negative implications.

3. Conclusions and next steps

The development of the Training Toolkit and the planning/organization of mentioned events were proceeding as outlined in the grant agreement. However, what was not predicted and taken into consideration is a health situation that has now reached almost every European country, namely the COVID-19. The pandemic paralysed traveling and the physical presence at workplaces (among many others) and hence many events and conferences along which WP6 planned its events are currently being cancelled, postponed or moved online. WP6 partners are looking for alternative solutions on engaging the SHSOC stakeholders in this current situation and exploring opportunities for organizing the SSHOC Stakeholders Forum in the autumn. WP6 partners are keen not to lose the momentum and are therefore aim to go ahead with some events in a possibly online format but are at the same time aware of the fact that engagement of participants in on-line meetings cannot substitute the ones done face to face.

4. List of appendices

Appendix 1: Purpose and scope document: EOSC thematic cloud stakeholder forum

Appendix 2: Revised proposed programme structure for the SSHOC Stakeholder forum

Appendix 3: Workshop description for the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at the IASSIST conference

Appendix 4: Workshop description for the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at the LIBER conference

Appendix 1

Purpose and scope document: EOSC THEMATIC CLOUDS STAKEHOLDER FORUM

EOSC THEMATIC CLOUDS STAKEHOLDER FORUM

Purpose and scope

This proposal describes the focus and scope of the EOSC thematic clouds Stakeholder Forum.

The main outcome of the “EOSC services, connections and the RDA” side-event at the RDA Plenary 14 in October 2019, the intention to continue to share best practices on cross-cluster topics and collaborate in stakeholder engagement.

The need for collaboration between the EOSC thematic clouds on the one hand and collection of end-user feedback led the SSHOC project to propose a joint mid-term Stakeholder Forum. All cluster projects have a similar duration and, when looking at the EOSC implementation plan, the cross-cluster activities will be developed along a similar timeline.

In January 2020 cluster coordinators agreed to the co-organisation of this stakeholder event.

This means:

- The event will be co-organised, budgets and tasks will be supported and carried out in equal participations.
- Branding of the event needs to be collaborative.
- Budget: some parts of the budget can be contributed in-kind (see estimated budget below).

ESOF 2020, 5-9 July, Trieste

When looking for an event to target researchers, the EOSC thematic end-user communities, from diverse domains, the [EuroScience Open Forum](#) 2020 was identified as a matching option for a side event for the following reasons:

- ESOF is the largest interdisciplinary meeting on science and innovation in Europe.
- It gathers over 4.500 thinkers, innovators, policy makers, journalists and educators from more than 90 countries, to discuss current and future breakthroughs in contemporary science.
- It is aligned with Open Science aims of the EOSC and the thematic clusters.
- The event is only organized every other year and the 2020 edition coincides with the mid-term need for stakeholder feedback for the project results a Stakeholder Forum (as per SSHOC GA mandate).

Aim of the EOSC Thematic Clouds Stakeholder Forum

Engagement with a broader range of stakeholders and other EU initiatives as primary goals of the Stakeholder Forum on the ongoing work of the cluster projects. A primary focus will be on engaging researchers in providing input in the ongoing work as well as foster collaboration and connections between researchers and other stakeholders categories:

- Researchers
- Policy Makers
- RIs
- Research Libraries and Archives
- Funders
- Industry

Engage stakeholders in discussions and hands-on sessions to collect their input on cross-cutting assets of the thematic clusters

- Marketplace
- Services & tools
- Connecting to Communities
- Governance

Forum organisers

Once an agreement on a collaborative stakeholder forum is set in place, a small and flexible organising committee should be set in place with representatives from each of the cluster projects, liaising within the individual projects on the next steps. At the time of writing of this purpose & scope document, the following people are involved in setting up the framework:

topic	Cluster project	team
Overall alignment & Agenda	SSHOC	Irena Vipavc Brvar Irena.Vipavc@fdv.uni-lj.si Ivana Ilijasic Versic ivana.versic@cessda.eu Marieke Willems m.willems@trust-itservices.com Martina Drascic martina.drascic@cessda.eu Martina Torma martina.torma@kb.nl Vasso Kalaitzi vasso.kalaitzi@KB.nl
	ENVRI FAIR	Magdalena Brus?
	PANOSC	Nicoletta Carboni?
	ESCAPE	Stephen Serjeant & Rita Meneses?
	EOSC-Life	Michael Raess

Hackathon	SSHOC	Carsten Thiel & Frank Fischer
	ENVRI-FAIR	Anca Heinola?
Promotion (liaisons with ESOF, plan)	PANOSC	Nicoletta Carboni?
Press Conference (international & local coverage)	EOSC-Life	Link to Trieste - BBMRI - ERIC Caitlin Ahern? Michael Raess?
Video	ESCAPE	Rita Meneses?
	SSHOC	Leonardo Marino?
Branding	ESCAPE	Rita Meneses?
	SSHOC	Filomena Minichiello?

Budget

Concept	Estimated cost in €	comment
Venue - University of Trieste	2000	1 auditorium + 5 rooms on 9 July
Catering (coffee + lunch) 50*200	10.000	Catering for 9 July
Video (live-streaming etc.)	5000	
Hackathon	7000	1 room (50 p.) + tech support + catering 8 & 9 July
Press conference (travel and meals 10 international journalists - 1 EU 2nd class travel + 2 nights à 150€/night + 75€/day for meals)	8000	Optional <i>SSHOC is liaising with ESOF to see if this could be done in collaboration.</i>
Camera + video editing	2000	This could be done as in-kind contribution
Collaterals in joint branding	2000	
5 Invited speakers - (travel, 2 nights, meals)	5000	
Social dinner (representatives cluster projects, 5 invited speakers, 40 participants hackathon + speakers)	5000	optional

Total	46.000	Clusters to discuss final budget based on possibilities and needs. Estimated cost per cluster project: 9.200€
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Agenda

Date and Place Stakeholder Forum: 9 July 2020, University of Trieste; Italy

Forum: 100 - 200 people

Date and Place Hackathon: 8 & 9 July 2020, University of Trieste; Italy

Hackathon proposal: see first definition by SSHOC below the agenda - needs input ENVRI-FAIR

Forum: 40 people

Time	Description	
8.30– 9.00	Registration	
9.00– 9.05	Event opening + EOSC (Marieke, Vasso, Irena??? Ron, Ivana?)	Hackathon 9-00-16.45
9.05– 9.30	<p>cluster projects pitching their project - invitation to their meet & greet area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOSC sustainability WG - Mirjam van Daalen? • ENVRI-FAIR for environmental research <i>Speaker:XXXXXXXX</i> • PaNOSC for multidisciplinary scientific analysis <i>Speaker:XXXXXXXX</i> • ESCAPE for astronomy and particle physics <i>Speaker:XXXXXXXX</i> • SSHOC for social sciences and humanities <i>Speaker: Ivana, Ron??</i> • EOSC-Life for life sciences <i>Speaker:XXXXXXXX</i> <p><i>Moderator: cluster projects representative XXXXX</i></p>	
9.30– 11.00	<p>Keynote lectures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Title 1 <i>Speaker 1 (name + organization) Researcher</i> • Title 2 <i>TBC (Kostas Glinos, European Commission) Funder/ EC representative</i> • Title 3 <i>Speaker 3 (name + organization) Research Library / Archive or RI</i> <p><i>Moderator: XXXXX</i></p>	

11.00– 11.30	Coffee break			Marketplace -
11.30– 12.15	Topic 1 Market place + summary of tools Speakers: representatives of all clusters XXXX <i>Moderator: XXXXX</i>			
12.15– 13.30	Demonstrations / Presentations			
	Parallel session 1 Tools SSH + disciplineX Speakers + concrete topic: XXXX <i>Moderator: XXXXX</i>	Parallel session 2 Tools Discipline XX Speakers: XXXX <i>Moderator: XXXXX</i>	Parallel session 3 Tools Discipline XX Speakers: XXXX <i>Moderator: XXXXX</i>	
13.30– 14.30	Networking lunch			
14.30– 15.30	Main joint topic 2 - targeted cross-cluster activities: Training & outreach Speakers: representatives of all clusters XXXX <i>Moderator: XXXXX</i>			
15.30– 15.45	Coffee break			
15.45– 16.45	Session title			
	Parallel session 1 Making data FAIR / Certificated Repositories + Legal & Ethical	Parallel session 2 Making data FAIR / Certificated Repositories + Legal & Ethical	Parallel session Making data FAIR / Certificated Repositories + Legal & Ethical	
16.45– 17.30	Reporting & call for action (Mirjam van Daalen and/or Franciska de Jong) & Wrapping up + outcomes hackathon			

Proposal for

Full-Day Hackathon: The SSH Open Marketplace as Exemplary Case for Discovery Layers of EOSC Cluster Projects

Alternative headline proposal: The SSH Open Marketplace and the Discovery Layers of EOSC Cluster Projects – Learning from Each Other and Adapting Best Practices

What?

Our one-and-a-half-day hackathon on July 8th/9th 2020 parallel to the EuroScience Open Forum in Trieste aims at gathering practical know-how around the ecosystem of the EOSC Marketplaces as they develop. We are particularly interested in exchange and learning from other clusters and EOSC projects and from researchers beyond the SSH.

Who?

The Social Sciences Open Humanities Cloud project (SSHOC) invites researchers and developers interested in advancing the discoverability in the EOSC domain. We particularly invite participants from other EOSC cluster projects (such as ENVRI-FAIR, PaNOSC, ESCAPE, EOSC-Life, but also new projects like TRIPLE) but also everyone beyond these project contexts. Within SSHOC the SSH Open Marketplace (accessible in an alpha version: <https://sshoc-marketplace.acdh-dev.oeaw.ac.at/>) connects datasets, tools, publications and workflows from all SSH fields (Social Sciences and Humanities) and increases their discoverability.

How?

In our hackathon we will compare and discuss challenges revolving around interoperability, provenance and contextualisation (or bluntly: technicalities and practicalities) around the development of catalogues and marketplaces. We will explore the front- and backend of the alpha version of the SSH Open Marketplace, but also discuss ways of involving the EOSC Portal in our development process. We are especially interested in learning from the discovery-related work in other EOSC projects.

Everybody is welcome. Depending on the attendance, the hackathon can assume the character of a focus group meeting to a code sprint or everything in-between. The attending SSHOC marketplace developers and information specialists will ensure a solid range of possible topics and questions.

Appendix 2

Revised proposed programme structure for the SSHOC Stakeholder forum

Time	Type and details of activity	Purpose
8.30 - 9.00	Registration	
9.00 - 9.10	Welcome by SSHOC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To shortly introduce the project and the purpose of the event To set expectations and briefly go through the event agenda
9.10 - 10.00	Keynote addresses from: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> EC/EOSC rep Research library/archive rep Researcher 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To set the tone and topic of the event To clarify event objectives To represent the different perspectives of different stakeholders
10.00 - 10.40	SSHOC Marketplace kick-off (interactive knowledge cafe with short tutorials on the tools already available and/or in development)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To kick off the marketplace and tools To receive feedback on the marketplace and tools
10.40 - 11.15	Speed dating with an expert (continuation of the marketplace kick-off without tutorials, just the experts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To receive less formal feedback on the tools To allow the participants to experience and ask questions one-on-one
11.15 - 11.45	Coffee break and the marketplace fair	Stands with tools available for “browsing” during the coffee break <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To network To receive more informal feedback on the tools To make the coffee break more interactive
11.45 - 12.45	Panel discussion with representatives of all stakeholder groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To receive feedback on project achievements and challenges so far To scope the direction and different perspectives of SSHOC development among the stakeholder groups To engage all stakeholders in a common activity

12.45 - 14.00	Networking lunch	
14.00 - 16.00	Workshop on the implementation of FAIR data principles OR Open Science	Interactive learning element <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To build a common understanding of the open science culture and FAIR principles among all the stakeholder groups
16.00 - 16.30	Presentation of Hackathon products/results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To include Hackathon as part of the stakeholder forum, and not a standalone event • To allow hackathon participants to pitch their ideas and interact with a wider stakeholder audience, possibly receive feedback and choose a winner
16.30 - 16.40	Final feedback session	
16.40 - 17.00	Closing	
17.00 - 18.30	Networking cocktails and snacks (finger food)	

Appendix 3

Workshop description for the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at the IASSIST conference

Title: SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp

Abstract

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a 40-month EU project which will create the SSH area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In this project, we want to contribute to a coordinated, pan-European training infrastructure by building and educating a network of SSH trainers involved in Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM) support.

The SSHOC Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp targets OS and RDM trainers and aims to help them improve their training and education programs for local researchers. The bootcamp will consist of three parts. First, we will provide an overview of available SSH training materials. Throughout SSHOC, existing and newly developed training materials will be collected and displayed in our SSHOC Train-the-trainer toolkit. Participants will receive an update of the toolkit and we will highlight key RDM and OS training materials that are already available. These include materials on for instance GDPR, sensitive data, FAIR and open data.

In the second part of the bootcamp, we will divide participants into smaller sub-groups for hands-on exercises where we will dive deeper into the materials and explore how they can be (re)used in everyone's own training practices. Depending on the background of the participants, we will focus on a selection of specific topics (e.g. FAIR data or GDPR) that we will further assess. Participants are encouraged to assess the usefulness of the existing materials for their own training and define opportunities and gaps.

The final part of the bootcamp will be an interactive session where we discuss training methods, exchange experiences, and provide tips to improve training skills. Topics that will be covered include the use of more interactive elements, preparations, evaluations and the development of learning objectives. We will close the workshop with a short plenary wrap-up.

Workshop - Learning Objectives:

By following this train-the-trainer bootcamp participants will

- Have up-to-date knowledge of available SSH training materials on RDM and Open Science
- Learn how these available materials can be re-used in SSH trainings
- Gain practical tips to increase the effectiveness of SSH trainings

Appendix 4

Workshop description for the Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp at the LIBER conference

Title workshop: SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp for Librarians

Date workshop: 24-6-2020

Timing workshop: 9:00 – 12:00

Coffee break: 10.30 – 11:00 AM (if possible: 10:00-10:15)

Minimum number of participants: 15 Maximum
number of participants: 60

Brief description of programme:

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) is a 40-month EU project which will create the SSH area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In this project, we also want to contribute to a coordinated, pan-European training infrastructure by building and educating a network of professionals involved in different areas of training and support for SSH researchers. The objectives of this training are a) to provide an introduction of the SSHOC train-the-trainer toolkit and facilitation of its use to improve training and education programs for local researchers, and b) hands-on session on existing materials and tools.

This SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamp targets Librarians and other professionals attending the LIBER conference and aims to help them improve their training and education programs for local researchers. The bootcamp will consist of three parts.

In the first part of the bootcamp, we will give an introduction to the SSHOC project, our training network and the train-the-trainer toolkit. The toolkit collects and displays existing and newly developed SSH training materials covering a variety of topics including, for instance, Research Data Management, GDPR, and FAIR data. We will encourage participants to discuss the usefulness of the existing materials for their own work and identify gaps that can be addressed within the SSHOC training network community.

In the second part of the bootcamp, we will dive deeper into using existing materials during a hands-on session. We will present the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (<https://vlo.clarin.eu>) and demonstrate how it can be used to search for, compare and access existing language resources of different types and

in different languages. We will also demonstrate the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard (<https://switchboard.clarin.eu>), a user-friendly facility that helps you find a matching language processing web application for your data. Among others, the toolkit contains guidance on how to identify, compare and use existing research datasets and tools, and to deposit new ones. CLARIN hosts a rich repository of language data suitable for scholars working in a wide range of disciplines in digital humanities, social sciences and beyond. In addition, it offers a wealth of tools to process the language data. Participants will have the opportunity to work in groups and try to find an answer to a specific user's question based on one of the four scenario templates: student, researcher, lecturer, citizen scientist.

After the hands-on session, we will finish the bootcamp with an interactive session discussing how the participants can develop and improve our own training activities. Next to reflecting on the use of the presented materials, we will discuss training methods and provide tips from the training network community to improve training skills. These discussions can center around topics such as the use of more interactive elements, preparations, evaluations and the development of learning objectives. The Training-of-Trainers Bootcamp will provide tools for participants to organise their own trainings upon completion of the bootcamp.

Timeline

- 15 min: Welcome and introduction
- 30 min: Resources: SSHOC Train-the-trainer toolkit
- 60 min: Hands-on session CLARIN [separated with the coffee break]
- 45 min: Methodologies: Let's boost our training activities
- 5 min: Evaluation and Closing